

Chemical constituents of *Artocarpus chaplasha*

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Abstract : Chemical investigation of the stem bark of *Artocarpus chaplasha* (Moraceae) afforded cycloartenyl acetate (1), 24-methylenecycloartanyl acetate (2), lupenyl acetate (3), (23*E*)-25-hydroxycycloart-23-en-3 β -ol (4), (23*E*)-25-methoxycycloart-23-en-3 β -ol (5), (23*E*)-25-hydroperoxycycloart-23-en-3 β -ol (6), β -sitosterol (7) and stigmasterol (8). Compounds 2, 4-6 and 8 are reported for the first time from this plant. The structures of all these known compounds have been established by spectral analysis.

Keywords : *Artocarpus chaplasha*, Moraceae, cycloartane derivatives.

Introduction

The genus *Artocarpus* (Moraceae) consists of about 47 species distributed in southeast Asia and Indo-Malaya¹. Several species of this genus have already been studied by several groups because they are rich source of triterpenes. *Artocarpus chaplasha* Roxb. (Local name : Cham, Chaplas) is used commercially as timber while the other Indian *Artocarpus* species, *A. lakoocha*, *A. integrifolia* and *A. hirsutus* have some recognition in the Indian indigenous system of medicine². Earlier work on the stem bark of *A. chaplasha* resulted in the isolation of lupenyl acetate, cycloartenyl acetate, isocycloartenyl acetate and β -sitosterol³. We report herein the isolation and identification of the known compounds, cycloartenyl acetate, 24-methylenecycloartanyl acetate, lupenyl acetate, (23*E*)-25-hydroxycycloart-23-en-3 β -ol, (23*E*)-25-methoxycycloart-23-en-3 β -ol, (23*E*)-25-hydroperoxycycloart-23-en-3 β -ol, β -sitosterol and stigmasterol from the stem bark of this plant.

The MeOH extract of the stem-bark of *A. chaplasha* was fractionated into petroleum ether, EtOAc and *n*-BuOH soluble fractions. The petroleum ether (PE) soluble fraction was the major fraction of MeOH extract. The PE fraction was column chromatographed on Si gel using petroleum ether and mixtures of petroleum ether-CHCl₃ and CHCl₃-EtOAc mixtures of increasing polarity. Fraction eluted with petroleum ether-CHCl₃ (70 : 30) afforded a white amorphous solid, named AC-1 (50 mg), m.p. 110–

113 °C. On TLC it showed a mixture of compounds of close *R_f* values. It showed positive Liebermann-Burchard test for terpenoids. Its IR spectrum showed the bands for hydroxyl (3450 cm⁻¹), acetate (1738 cm⁻¹) and olefinic double bond (1647 and 883 cm⁻¹) functions. Its ¹H NMR spectrum showed a pair of doublets at δ 0.34 and 0.57 indicating the presence of cyclopropane ring. The solid was subjected to HPLC on reversed phase (C₁₈) using MeOH and MeOH-CH₂Cl₂ as mobile phases. Fractions eluted with MeOH-CH₂Cl₂ yielded three compounds, **1** (15 mg), **2** (6 mg) and **3** (4 mg). Compound **1**, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺ 468) was recrystallised from Me₂CO as colorless needles, m.p. 118 °C. EIMS of the compound showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 468 and other significant mass peaks at *m/z* 408, 393, 365, 297, 286, 271, 175, 109 and 69 (base peak). The 600 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃) displayed signals at δ 4.57 (m, *J*_{AX} + *J*_{BX} = 15.3 Hz), a pair of doublets at δ 0.34 and 0.57 (each 1H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz), a methyl singlet at δ 0.96, a methyl doublet at δ 0.88 (3H, d, *J* 5.6 Hz) and an olefinic proton at δ 5.10 (1H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz), assigned to H-3, H₂-19, H₃-18, H₃-21 and H-24 protons, respectively. The 150 MHz ¹³C NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ recorded significant signals at δ _C 80.67 (C-3), 125.24 (C-24), 130.87 (C-25), 21.30 and 170.97 (AcO-3) and other signals characteristic of cycloartane skeleton. The compound was characterized as cycloartenyl acetate by comparison of its spectral data with those reported in

the literature⁴. Compound **2**, C₃₃H₅₄O₂ (M⁺ 482) was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 115–117 °C. Its FAB-MS showed quasi-molecular ion peak at *m/z* 483 [M+H]⁺ and other mass peaks at *m/z* 423, 408, 407, 95, 43 (base peak). Its 600 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ showed signals for four tertiary methyls [δ 0.85 (3H, s, H₃-30), 0.89 (6H, s, H₃-28, 29) and 0.96 (3H, s, H₃-18)], three methyl doublets [δ 0.91 (3H, d, *J* 5.8 Hz, H₃-21) and 1.06 (6H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, H₃-26, 27)], two cyclopropane protons [δ 0.34 and 0.57 (each d, *J* 3.9 Hz, H₂-19)]; an acetoxymethine group [δ 4.57 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3 and 6.0 Hz, H-3), 2.05 (3H, s, Ac)] and two exomethylene protons [δ 4.67 and 4.72 (each br s, H₂-31)] suggesting methylene-cycloartanyl acetate like structure. The 150 MHz ¹³C NMR spectrum recorded 33 carbon signals including significant signals at δ 80.85 (C-3), 157.06 (C-24), 33.91 (C-25), 29.89 (C-19), 171.13 and 21.09 (AcO-3), 106.08 (C-31) and other signals corroborating the said skeletal structure. The compound was identified as 24-methylenecycloartanyl acetate by comparison of its spectral data with those reported in the literature⁴. Compound **3**, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺ 468) was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 218 °C. It was identified as lupenyl acetate by comparison of its spectral data (IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and EI-MS) with those reported in the literature⁵.

The fraction eluted with CHCl₃-EtOAc (90 : 10) mixture gave a white solid, named AC-2 (28 mg), m.p. 150–152 °C. It responded to positive Liebermann-Burchard test for steroids. On TLC it showed to be a mixture of three components. Its IR spectrum showed the bands for hydroxyl (3419 cm⁻¹) and olefinic (1642 cm⁻¹) functions. It was subjected to HPLC on C₁₈ column using H₂O-MeOH, MeOH and MeOH-CH₂Cl₂ mixtures as mobile phases. The fraction eluted with MeOH gave compound **4** (4 mg), compound **5** (2.5 mg), compound **6** (8 mg), and compounds **7** and **8** as mixture (2 mg). Compound **4**, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442) showed quasi-molecular ion peak at *m/z* 443 [M+H]⁺ in FAB-MS. The ¹H NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ displayed signals for a cyclopropane ring [δ 0.33 and 0.55 (each 1H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz, H₂-19)], six tertiary methyls [δ 0.81 (3H, s, H₃-30), 0.88 (3H, s, H₃-28), 0.97 (6H, s, H₃-18, 29) and 1.34 (6H, s, H₃-26, 27)], one methyl doublet [δ 0.87 (3H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, H₃-21)], an

alcoholic methine [δ 3.38 (1H, m, H-3)] and two AB type olefinic protons [δ 5.70 (1H, ddd, *J* 15.8, 8.0, 5.5 Hz, H-23) and 5.52 (1H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz, H-24)] suggesting 3,25-dihydroxycycloartanol like structure having a *trans*-olefinic double bond. The ¹³C/DEPT NMR spectrum of the compound in CDCl₃ showed 30 carbon signals including signals at δ 78.92 (C-3), 125.6 (C-23), 139.44 (C-24), 29.11 (C-26), 29.87 (C-27), 70.73 (C-25), characteristic of cycloart-23-en-3β-25-diol structure. It was identified as (23*E*)-cycloart-23-ene-3β-25-diol by comparison of its spectral data with literature. Compound **5**, C₃₁H₅₂O₂ (M⁺ 456), white amorphous solid, showed quasi-molecular ion at *m/z* 457 [M+H]⁺ in its FAB-MS. In ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃) it displayed proton signals very similar to that of compound **4** except a methoxy signal at δ 3.49 (3H, s), two methyl singlet at δ 1.31 (6H, s). In ¹³C NMR spectrum in CDCl₃, it displayed carbon signals similar to those of compound **4** except for the olefinic carbons at δ 127.52 (C-23) and 136.62 (C-24), methoxy carbon at δ 50.10, two quaternary methyl carbons at δ 26.0 (C-26) and 26.1 (C-27), and C-25 carbon at δ 73.50. Possibly β- and γ- effects of the methoxyl group at C-25 resulted shielding and deshielding effects on the olefinic carbons, C-24 and C-23, respectively. It was identified as (23*E*)-25-methoxycycloart-23-en-3β-ol by comparison of its spectral data with those reported in the literature^{6,7}. Compound **6**, C₃₀H₅₀O₃ (M⁺ 458), colorless needles, m.p. 130 °C, showed quasi-molecular ion peak at *m/z* 459 [M+H]⁺ along with significant mass ions at *m/z* 441, 425, 409, 393, 255, 175 and 121 (base peak) in its FAB-MS. Its ¹H NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ showed proton signals similar to that of compound **4** including a hydroperoxy signal at δ 7.32 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O). Its ¹³C/DEPT NMR spectrum showed carbon signals similar to those of compound **4** except diagnostic carbon signals at δ 130.87 (C-23), 134.40 (C-24), 82.30 (C-25), 24.38 (C-26) and 24.32 (C-27). The hydroperoxy group at C-25 caused more deshielding of C-25 and C-23 carbons and shielding of C-24 carbon. The compound was identified as (23*E*)-25-hydroperoxycycloart-23-en-3β-ol by comparison of its spectral data with those reported in the literatures⁸. Compounds **7** and **8** obtained as a mixture (2 : 1), were identified as β-sitosterol and stigmasterol by com-

On HPLC analysis AC-1 afforded compounds **1**, **2** and **3**; while AC-2 gave compounds **4-8**.

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